

A New Synthesis of Methionine⁵-Enkephalin[†]

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Synthesis of the endogenous opiate, methionine⁵-enkephalin, by stepwise elongation of the peptide chain from C-terminus using 2,4,5-trichlorophenyl active esters of *t*-butoxycarbonyl amino acids is described. The preparation of intermediate peptides Boc-Gly-Phe-Met-OMe[†] (2), Boc-Gly-Gly-Phe-Met-OMe (3), Boc-Tyr-Gly-Gly-Phe-Met-OMe (4) and Boc-Tyr-Gly-Gly-Phe-Met (5) in high yields is also reported.

THE discovery of opioid peptides¹⁻⁵, which act as endogenous ligands for the highly selective opiate receptors, may be regarded as a major breakthrough towards understanding the mode of action of narcotic analgesics and the phenomenon of addiction and tolerance associated with them. Among these peptides, now commonly referred to by the generic name 'endorphins', enkephalin was the first to be isolated from mammalian brain. It was found to be a mixture of two pentapeptides, Tyr-Gly-Gly-Phe-Met and Tyr-Gly-Gly-Phe-Leu, called methionine-enkephalin and leucine-enkephalin respectively⁷. The amino acid sequence of methionine-enkephalin (Met⁵-enkephalin) corresponds to residues 61-65 of β -lipotropin, a 91 amino acid pituitary peptide⁸, and is common to all the β -lipotropin related pituitary endorphins^{9,10} at their N-terminus. Although the exact biosynthetic origin of enkephalins is not yet clear, the failure to detect long chain opioid peptides in the brain suggests that enkephalins are the sole opioid peptides in the brain that may mediate pain perception¹¹. Despite its high analgesic potential, enkephalin suffers a serious drawback because of its being very susceptible to proteolytic attack^{3,12}. It was, therefore, of interest to explore the possibility of developing a suitable analogue of enkephalin which would not only be a powerful analgesic but would also be relatively more stable and non-addictive. In order that a suitable and convenient procedure for the synthesis of peptides analogous to Met⁵-enkephalin be standardized, the synthesis of Met⁵-enkephalin itself was attempted first and this is now reported. Since this work was started, reports describing the synthesis of the two enkephalins¹³⁻¹⁶ and their more potent analogues have already appeared¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

The synthetic strategy adopted by us differs from that followed by others in that the classical procedure involving stepwise elongation of the peptide chain from the C-terminal end has been employed (Scheme 1). Another important feature of this synthesis is the use of 2, 4, 5-trichlorophenyl active esters^{20,21} for the formation of the peptide bond. These active esters can

be conveniently prepared and stored in the laboratory and give good yields of the required peptides in a high state of purity. As per expectation, the yields of the intermediate peptides at every stage of the synthesis

are higher than reported by others. For the protection of α -amino functions the *t*-butoxycarbonyl group has been employed as its cleavage from the protected derivatives could be brought about with TFA under mild conditions. The carboxy group of the C-terminal methionine residue has been protected as the methyl ester, but the tyrosine phenolic hydroxy group has been kept unprotected. Thus, starting from Boc-Phe-Met-OMe²⁰ (1) the protected pentapeptide Boc-Tyr-Gly-Gly-Phe-Met-OMe (4) was obtained in good yield as a crystalline solid which melted at 105° (Lit¹⁴ 92°) and was chromatographically homogeneous. Saponification of peptide 4 followed by the treatment of the

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** Abbreviations according to IUPAC-IUB Commission on biochemical nomenclature (ref. 25). Other abbreviations: Tcp, 2,4,5-trichlorophenyl; DMF, dimethylformamide; TFA, trifluoroacetic acid; BuOH, butanol; AcOH, acetic acid; EtOAc, ethyl acetate.

product with TFA afforded the required pentapeptide as its trifluoroacetate. This material was further purified on DEAE-Sephadex A-25 according to the procedure described by Bower *et al*¹⁵ to give pure Met⁵-enkephalin as a white microcrystalline solid

Experimental

Uncorrected capillary melting points are reported. Homogeneity of all the peptides was established by TLC on silica gel G plates, using the following solvent systems: A, *n*-BuOH-AcOH-H₂O (3:1:1); B, CHCl₃-MeOH (9:1). N-Protected peptides were revealed by spraying TLC plates with 2N HBr/AcOH followed by ninhydrin reagent (0.2% in acetone). Optical rotations were determined with a JASCO DIP-180 automatic polarimeter.

N-t-Butoxycarbonylglycyl-L-phenylalanyl-L-methionine methyl ester (2) :

Boc-Phe-Met-OMe²² (4.1 g, 0.01 mole) was treated with TFA (10 ml) at 0° under stirring for 30 min. After the removal of TFA under reduced pressure, the oily residue was triturated with ether, the solid product filtered, and washed thoroughly with ether. The crude TFA salt, thus obtained, was dried under vacuum over KOH, dissolved in DMF (5 ml) and the solution chilled to 0°. The cold solution was neutralized with Et₃N (1.4 ml, 0.01 mole), mixed with a solution of Boc-Gly-OTcp²³ (4.3 g, 0.012 mole) in dioxan (50 ml) and the mixture allowed to stand at room temperature for 48 hr with occasional shaking. The solvent was removed under vacuum, the residue taken up in EtOAc (50 ml) and the solution washed successively with 1% aq. Et₃N solution, 10% citric acid and water. The organic phase was separated, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, and the oily product, obtained after removal of the solvent, triturated with pet. ether. The solid material was recrystallized from EtOAc-pet. ether. yield 4 g (87%), m.p. 69-71°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -15.5^\circ$ (c 2 in DMF), Rf (B) 0.73 (Found: C, 56.39; H, 7.19; N, 8.9. Calc. for C₂₂H₃₃N₃O₆S: C, 56.53; H, 7.39; N, 8.78 per cent).

N-t-Butoxycarbonylglycylglycyl-L-phenylalanyl-L-methionine methyl ester (3) :

Boc-Gly-Phe-Met-OMe (2) (4.67 g, 0.01 mole) was treated with TFA (10 ml) for the removal of the Boc group as described for peptide 1 and the resulting trifluoroacetate dissolved in DMF (5 ml). The solution was chilled to 0°, neutralized with Et₃N (1.4 ml, 0.01 mole), mixed with a solution of Boc-Gly-OTcp (4.3 g, 0.012 mole) in dioxan (30 ml) and stirred at 0° for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stand at room temperature for 36 hr with occasional stirring followed by the removal of the solvent under reduced pressure. The residue was dissolved again in EtOAc (50 ml), the solution washed with 1% aq. Et₃N solution followed by 10% citric acid and water, dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under vacuum. The residual solid was recrystallized from EtOAc-pet. ether; yield 4.5g (85%), m. p. 78-80°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -13^\circ$ (c 1 in MeOH), Rf (B) 0.46 (Found: C, 54.72;

H, 6.90; N, 10.51. Calc. for C₂₄H₃₆N₄O₇S: C, 54.96; H, 6.87; N, 10.69 per cent).

N-t-Butoxycarbonyl-L-tyrosylglycylglycyl-L-phenylalanyl-L-methionine methyl ester (4) :

The protected tetrapeptide 3 (1.05 g, 0.002 mole) was treated with TFA (3 ml) as usual and the resulting trifluoroacetate dissolved in DMF (2 ml). The solution was treated with Et₃N (0.28 ml, 0.002 mole) at 0° followed by the addition of Boc-Tyr-OTcp²⁴ (1 g, 0.002 mole) in DMF (3 ml) and the reaction mixture stored at room temperature for 36 hr with occasional shaking. DMF was distilled off under vacuum, the residue taken up in EtOAc, the EtOAc solution washed successively with 1% aq. Et₃N solution, 10% citric acid and water and then dried over Na₂SO₄. The solid obtained after the evaporation of the solvent under reduced pressure was recrystallized from EtOAc-pet ether; yield 0.91 g (70%), m.p. 105° (Lit¹⁴ 92°), $[\alpha]_D^{25} -10^\circ$ (c 2 in MeOH), -23° (c 1 in DMF), (Lit¹⁴ $[\alpha]_D^{25} -20.2^\circ$ (c 2 in DMF), Rf (B) 0.37 (Found: C, 57.57; H, 6.47; N, 10.08. Calc. for C₃₃H₄₅N₅O₉S: C, 57.63; H, 6.55; N, 10.19 per cent).

N-t-Butoxycarbonyl-L-tyrosylglycylglycyl-L-phenylalanyl-L-methionine (5) :

A solution of Boc-Tyr-Gly-Gly-Phe-Met-OMe (0.2g, 0.0003 mole) in MeOH-water mixture (4:1; 1.5 ml) was mixed with 2N NaOH (0.29 ml, 0.0006 mole) at room temperature and stirred for 2 hr. After the removal of MeOH under reduced pressure and acidification of the solution with 5% citric acid (pH 2) the pentapeptide acid precipitated out. It was extracted with EtOAc, the organic phase washed several times with saturated sodium chloride solution and dried over Na₂SO₄. The solvent was distilled off under vacuum leaving behind a white solid which was recrystallized from MeOH-ether. yield 0.19 g (98%), m.p. 135-40°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -18.5^\circ$ (c 1 in DMF), Rf (A) 0.92 (Found: C, 56.9; H, 6.43; N, 10.22. Calc. for C₃₂H₄₃N₅O₉S: C, 57.05; H, 6.39; N, 10.41 per cent).

L-Tyrosylglycylglycyl-L-phenylalanyl-L-methionine (6) (Met⁵-enkephalin) :

Boc-Tyr-Gly-Gly-Phe-Met (5) (0.3 g, 0.0004 mole) was added to TFA (5 ml) containing anisole (0.2 ml) at 0° and the mixture stirred for 30 min at the same temperature. After the removal of TFA under vacuum, the oily residue was triturated with dry ether to give a white solid. The solid product was washed thoroughly with dry ether and then crystallized from MeOH-ether. The partially purified material weighed 0.276 g (90%). Further purification of this solid on DEAE-Sephadex A-25 (acetate form) using 1% pyridine-0.04% AcOH aqueous buffer (pH 6) for elution as reported by Bower and coworkers¹⁵ gave chromatographically homogeneous Met⁵-enkephalin. yield 0.147 g (65%), m.p. 196-98°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -21^\circ$ (c 1 in DMF), Rf (A) 0.5. (Found: C, 56.43; H, 6.0; N, 12.1. Calc. for C₂₇H₃₈N₅O₇S: C, 56.5; H, 6.15; N, 12.2 per cent).

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